

Challenges to Aquatic Food Source Sustainability: Investigating the Bioaccumulation of Microplastics of Tilapia and Mussels

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Abstract

Microplastics are small plastic particles measuring less than 5 mm in diameter, have emerged as a pervasive environmental pollutant in aquatic ecosystems worldwide. Food from aquatic sources has been contaminated. This study investigates the microplastics from food aquatic resources and the potential consequences for human health. By conducting field sampling and laboratory analysis, the researchers evaluate the distribution and prevalence of microplastics in Tilapia and Mussels caught from Laguna de Bay. The researchers utilized the Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy on analysing the data and to create a comprehensive interpretation of results. The results show that microplastics are present in the intestine of the caught samples for both Tilapia and Mussels. These findings provide insight into the composition of the sample, highlighting the presence of Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), with the Infrared spectrum of the sample matches that of chlorinated polyethylene, which is a type of microplastic. This shows that when cooked and eaten, contaminated aquatic food can deliver microplastics to the human body through bioaccumulation. This could also result to biomagnification of the ingested microplastics as the humans consume more of this aquatic food source. When an individual ingests a microplastics it could manifest to diseases and lead to serious complications like Cardiovascular Disease, Impaired Kidney and Liver function, Development of Metabolic Disorders, Neurological Effects and Reproductive and Developmental Issues. Further evaluation on the types of microplastics present among other aquatic food sources must be investigated as well.

Keywords: *Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, Laguna de Bay, polyethylene, mussels, tilapia.*

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Introduction

Microplastics are categorized into primary and secondary types. Primary microplastics were originally produced to be less than 5 mm in size, while secondary microplastics result from the breakdown of larger items. Micro and nano plastics are so tiny, they cannot be filtered out by wastewater treatment systems; as a result, these plastic particles end up in the rivers, oceans, and freshwater supply systems (Yee, 2021). It is for this reason that the bioaccumulation of microplastics from aquatic habitats becomes more possible and poses higher risks of interfering with the physiology of animals, especially those that are being consumed by humans (Bhuyan, 2022). The Philippines ranks among the top contributors to plastic pollution in marine coastal areas, prompting the necessity for regulatory measures; however, there remains a gap in understanding the correlation between the nation's plastic regulations and the evolving

research on both macroplastics and microplastics (MPs) (Galarpe et al., 2021). The current assessment highlights methodological and technological challenges hindering the identification of sources, assessment of fluxes, and understanding of socio-environmental influences on macroplastics. Suffice to say, research on macroplastics and MPs in the Philippines is still in its nascent stage. This study quantifies the levels of microplastics in seafood products, specifically Tilapia and Mussels, that were being sold in the public market and discusses the potential harm of microplastics in human health. Additionally, it underscores the pathways through which these particles may enter the human body and outlines the harmful effects observed in marine organisms due to microplastic ingestion.

Materials and Methods

Seafood Collection and Preparation

This research project focused on the presence and effects of microplastics in two aquatic species, *Oreochromis niloticus* (Tilapia) and *Perna viridis* (Green-lipped Mussel) collected from the Laguna de Bay, Philippines. The researchers selected alive *Oreochromis niloticus* (Tilapia) with a minimum weight of 350 grams each. On the other hand, 30 pieces of *Perna viridis* were collected with a shell length ranging from 10cm to 15cm. After the samples were safely brought to the laboratory, the researchers performed dissection. Three types of tissues of tilapia were prepared, the flesh, the intestine and the bones of the tilapia. For the mussels, only the edible parts were included. A 100g of each of the tissues of the *Oreochromis niloticus* and 100g of the edible part of the *Perna viridis* were placed on separated beakers. Each of the collected parts and samples were subjected to chemical digestion.

Chemical Digestion

The researchers incubated the tissues submerged in KOH solution at 40°C for 48 hours for the best treatment of the samples. However, at 50 and 60 °C, it damaged PET, which leads to the decrease of the recovery rate of PET and PVC. The treatment of 10% KOH solution and ferrous sulfate incubating at 40°C was both time and cost-effective, efficient in digesting biological materials, and had no effect on the plastic polymer's integrity.

After incubation, 30% hydrogen peroxide was added per beaker. In addition, 30mL of potassium hydroxide and 20mL of ferrous sulfate to each beaker. The mixture was then stirred to 350rpm for 1hr. After 1hr after using the magnetic stirrer in maintaining all temperatures, the potassium hydroxide, ferrous sulfate and KOH solution were completely separated from biological matrices through filtration. (Ferrante et al, 2022)

Microplastic Identification

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, a method for examining material composition through the measurement of infrared light absorption, emission, or reflection was used to identify PET presence from the samples. This technique furnishes comprehensive insights into the molecular structure of substances, facilitating the detection and measurement of diverse compounds. According to Chen et al., (2020), Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is currently the predominant method utilized for detecting and measuring microplastics (MPs).

Results

Flesh Tissues of *Oreochromis niloticus*

There is a broad significant peak at around 3310.60/cm which corresponds to OH vibration (see Figure 1). There is a peak at 2922.81/cm and 2852.43/cm which corresponds to C-H vibration while a peak at 1743.63/cm corresponding to C=O stretching probably of a carboxylic acid group and 1644.53/cm which pertains to C=C aromatic vibration. Common microplastics do not contain any OH groups. The

closest spectra that can be obtained from the sample is lecithin, a fat that can be obtained from animal tissues. Lecithin has an ester or carboxylic acid group and a double bond which corresponds to peaks 1743 and 1644/cm respectively. Fatty Acids are also present in the flesh in which possibly the fatty acids are extracted. The closest polymer that matches the spectrum is Polyacrylamide. However, the amide stretching ranges from 1650 to 1700/cm while the carboxylic acid C=O stretches in 1700 to 1750/cm in which the spectrum shows the presence of a carboxylic acid group. Polycarbonates contain an ester group, but the IR spectrum of polycarbonates do not show any significant peaks at around 3000 to 3500/cm. Based on the IR spectrum, the compound does not show any microplastics.

Figure 1. The Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) Reading for the Flesh Tissue Sample of *Oreochromis niloticus*

Figure 2. The Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) Reading for the Intestine Tissue Sample of *Oreochromis niloticus*

Intestine Tissues of *Oreochromis niloticus*

There are sharp peaks at 2849/cm and 2918/cm which correspond to C-H stretching. The broad peak at around 3300/cm corresponds to O-H bond vibration but unlike the other samples, the intensity of the peak is relatively small. The peaks in 1742/cm, 1648/cm, 1577/cm, 1541/cm, and 1466/cm as compared with other samples were weak and these signals can somehow be related to the background. There is a sharp strong peak at around 1000/cm which corresponds to C-X bond vibration. Based on the library of polymer, the spectrum matches the chlorinated polyethylene, an example of a microplastic. There are two peaks in the IR spectrum of chlorinated polyethylene that appear at 2850 and 2900/cm as well as medium peak at 1000 to 1150/cm. However, the polymer does not contain any peaks at 3300/cm

where in the sample, there is a broad relatively weak signal. According to one study, the presence of OH peak on spectrum of microplastic is due to oxidation or degradation of microplastics due to weathering. Based on the IR spectrum, the sample contains chlorinated polyethylene which is microplastic. (See Figure 2)

Bone Tissues of *Oreochromis niloticus*

As shown in Figure 3, there are notable peaks at approximately 3300/cm which corresponds to O-H stretching. There are also peaks at 2853/cm and 2922/cm which correspond to CH vibration. The presence of unsaturation in the compound can be supported by peaks at 3010/cm which corresponds to C=C-H stretching and 1667/cm which indicates the presence of C=C bond vibration. In addition, the presence of a carboxylic acid group can be seen by the peak in 1743/cm. Most microplastics do not have an OH group. The closest spectra that match from the library is a fatty acid from sesame oil or castor oil. This can be supported by the presence of a broad peak from 2750/cm to 3500/cm that overlaid the signals from C=C-H and C-H bond stretching which is an OH bond and the peak in 1743/cm which is a carbonyl from carboxylic acid. Fatty acids are widely found in tissues and like flesh samples, it was the compound extracted. The nearest polymer that matches the spectrum is low density polyethylene. The polymer matches the sample at peaks 2800 and 2900/cm. However, the polymer does not have any peaks at 1600 and 1750/cm. The spectrum of the polymer has a medium sharp peak at 1450/cm at fingerprint region. Based on IR spectrum, the sample does not contain any microplastics.

Figure 3. The Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) Reading for the Bone Tissue Sample of *Oreochromis niloticus*

Edible Tissues of *Perna viridis* (Tahong)

One of the notable peaks in the spectrum is 3343/cm broad peak which corresponds to O-H vibration of the bond. There are also small peaks at 2853/cm and 2927/cm which correspond to C-H vibration. These peaks are associated with different vibrations of C-H bonds. There is a small peak at 1648/cm which corresponds to C=C vibrations. The spectrum of the compound matches that of a mineral which is possible because mussels are rich in minerals. The closest compounds based on the polymer library are polyacetylene and ethylene vinyl alcohol. However, polyacetylene does not have any broad peaks at 3000 to 3500/cm as the compound does not have any OH groups. On the other hand, ethylene vinyl alcohol has a sharp peak at 2850 to 2900/cm at diagnostic region while 850, 1350, and 1450/cm for fingerprint region. Based on the IR spectrum, the tahong samples do not contain any microplastics. (See Figure 4)

Figure 4. The Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) Reading for the Edible Tissue Sample of *Perna viridis*

Discussion

Microplastics enter human bodies through contaminated food and water sources due to environmental pollution and dietary habits. The process begins with ingestion, where consumers unintentionally allow these invaders into the body (Yuan & Cummins, 2022). The environment is becoming increasingly polluted with plastic due to poor trash management and industrial runoff (Osman et al., 2023). Microplastics can also be ingested through contaminated seafood, agricultural produce, and drinking water, breaching the intestinal barrier and circulating through the bloodstream to accumulate in organs like the liver, kidneys, and adipose tissue over time (Ziani et al., 2023).

Microplastics can contaminate fish resources and most of them are species that are primarily consumed and sold in the public markets; Furthermore, these contaminants may enter fish's liver and brain in addition to their digestive tracts (Alberghini et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2018). In addition, Zhang et al., 2022, MPs ingested by fish larvae could accumulate in the gill, liver, and intestines and then cause physical sore and noticeable histopathological changes in the liver, gallbladder, and intestinal organs. The findings revealed a low to non-existent presence of microplastics in the head and flesh of tilapia, supporting the notion that microplastic accumulation may be more prevalent in other parts of the fish, such as the gastrointestinal tract, rather than in muscle tissues or head regions.

Addressing these serious issues requires increased awareness, regulation of plastic pollution, and sustainable practices to safeguard human health and the environment. As humans classify fish as one of the major sources of protein and food nutrients. Microplastics disperse across the aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. They influence food safety and the environment, and they are particularly challenging to overcome (Aryani et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The intestine samples exhibited a notably high density of microplastics, indicating potential accumulation or ingestion pathways within the digestive system of these aquatic organisms, specifically Tilapia. As per the Green Lipped mussels, microplastics are widespread in aquatic environments, but are not detected from the samples of this study. These findings underscore the urgent need for further investigation into the sources and pathways of microplastic contamination in aquatic ecosystems. Microplastics have been

shown that it can be bioaccumulated within the food chain and ultimately pose risks to human health upon consumption of contaminated seafood. These findings underscore the urgent need for further investigation into the sources and pathways of microplastic contamination in aquatic ecosystems.

The study helps to better understand the scope and effects of microplastic contamination is further highlighted by this result, which highlights the urgent need for comprehensive steps to limit plastic pollution. In addition, this study offers insightful information on the many routes via which marine species may ingest microplastic, which has consequences for human and environmental health. To effectively mitigate the negative impacts of plastic pollution and safeguard the integrity of marine ecosystems for future generations.

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Conflict of Interests

We declare that no conflict of interest occurred during and after the conduct of this research. It is also declared that this research is novel and unique and was conducted by the researchers first and foremost.

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